

Neuroinflammatory Crosstalk: The Impact of PAR-1 Activation in Multiple Sclerosis Pathogenesis

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ABSTRACT

Multiple sclerosis (MS), an autoimmune disease induced by CD-4 T Cells. It makes the effector T cells resistant to regulatory mechanisms primarily induced upon their association with CD4 FoxP3+ regulatory T cells (Tregs). Moreover, there is also a strong association between Kv1.3 and calcium channels which inter play a fundamental role to understand the alterations induced in the T lymphocytes, one of them being the self-reactive state of the receptor which contributes towards the progression of MS. The self-reactive state of T cells makes them capable of causing damage to the neurons via various independent pathways like releasing Granzyme B (GrB). Ultimately, Grb derives the cleavage of PAR-1 in neurons, governing the activation of the receptor and then increasing the expression of Kv1.3 channels and subsequently activating Notch-1 receptor. The receptor is rendered immune to all regulatory mechanisms. This contributes towards the exacerbation of neuronal damage and progression of the disease. Understanding how the T cell receptor is hijacked by the respective ligands and the corresponding self-reactive state of TCR can assist in developing drugs or therapies to control the resultant inflammatory cascade in the central nervous system (CNS).

Keywords: Neuroinflammation, Multiple Sclerosis MS, PAR-1 Activation, Cell signaling, Neurobiology

INTRODUCTION

Multiple Sclerosis (MS) is an autoimmune disease of the central nervous system (CNS) typically known for inflammatory and demyelinating lesions as well as neuronal loss. The disease can relapse, remit or progress towards severity. The lesions can occur at different stages of the disease as well as in different perimeters of CNS (1). Thus, clinically, MS being a chronic disease can be stable or it can progress rapidly as a crippling illness. The activation of T

cell holds a pivotal part in causing inflammatory lesions and neurite damage typical for Multiple Sclerosis. Neurological damage in this autoimmune disease is linked with the amount of T-cells which are able to pass the blood/brain barrier (BBB) and are passaged to the CNS. The cells which enter a self-reactive state are capable of causing damage to the neurons via direct contact as well as through independent pathways like releasing Granzyme B (GrB) (2,3). GrB drives the neuronal cytotoxicity via various membrane receptors e.g. mannose 6-phosphate receptor or through cleaving and associating with membrane bound receptors, one of them being Notch-1. Notch-1 receptor supports formation of the inflammatory/demyelinating lesions in Multiple Sclerosis leading towards neuronal damage.

The GPCR based Protease Activated Receptor 1 (PAR1) is a serine protease based GPCR. It is present in neurons and glial cells. The activation of PAR-1 which initiates tau phosphorylation mediates neuronal damage in motor neurons (4). It has been proven via experimental studies that Grb derives the cleavage of PAR-1 in neurons, mediating the activation of the receptor and then increasing the expression of Kv1.3 channels and subsequently activating Notch-1 receptor. This contributes towards the exacerbation of neuronal damage and progression of the disease

Normal cellular signaling pathway

T-Cell Antigen Receptor (TCR)

T Cell activation results in either cytotoxicity of the targeted cells or activation of B cells to produce antibodies. This activation of T Cell to yield a productive response within a cell requires two signals. Any foreign antigen serves as a primary signal to activate the pathway to produce T cell. The foreign ligand binds to T-Cell Antigen Receptor (TCR) based around the idea of class II major histocompatibility complex (MHC). It is a complex structure of six different polypeptides. The clonotypic α and β chains govern ligand specificity via genetic rearrangement that contributes to yield multiple receptor variants. However, the intracellular response is governed by the invariant parts of TCR i.e. δ , γ , and ϵ also called the CD3 complex along with the ζ chains (5). The interconnecting co receptors like CD28 or CD4 with antigen presenting cell (APC) serve as secondary signals in TCR signaling pathway.

TRC/ Ca²⁺ dependent signaling and CRAC channel

Protein Tyrosine phosphorylation is the key signaling pathway which follows upon activation of TCR. It leads to a downstream signaling cascade which have been known to stimulate various transcription factors (TF) like NF- κ B, NF- κ B and AP-1. The TF dictate the production of genes required for T cell response. Firstly, the TCR is ligated by the MHC complex which dictates the activation of Lck (SRC family protein tyrosine kinases) (6). They phosphorylate the invariant components of TCR complex which leads to recruitment of ZAP-70 (tyrosine kinase), LAT and SLP-76

(adaptor linker proteins) (7). LAT and SLP-76 are phosphorylated which then leads to activation of Phospholipase Cy1 (PLC γ 1). This leads to activation of secondary messengers i.e. inositol 1,4,5- triphosphate (IP $_3$). IP $_3$ functions to trigger an intracellular calcium flux which is an indispensable step during the productive activation of T cell. As depicted in the pathway given below, activation of PLC γ 1 governs the formation of IP $_3$ which then binds to the IP $_3$ receptor located on the membrane of endoplasmic reticulum (ER). There is a continuous outward flux of Calcium from the ER which eventually drains the calcium reserve. This triggers the activation of Calcium release-activated calcium channel (CRAC) located on the plasma membrane. This allows calcium to be driven within the cell in order to maintain a high intracellular calcium throughput. However, entrance of calcium leads to depolarisation of the membrane and to counter this, voltage-gated potassium channels are opened. In case of T cell activation Kv1.3 channels are opened. The influx of calcium is balance by efflux of potassium through the plasma membrane and this prevents membrane depolarisation.

Figure 1: TCR/ Ca²⁺ dependent signaling and CRAC channel (15)

DISEASED PATHWAY IN MULTIPLE SCLEROSIS

Multiple sclerosis is predominantly a disease induced by the T-Cells of the inflammatory system (8). The above normal pathway for activation of T cell is hijacked and TCR enters a self-reactive state, that is, it awaits no specific ligand to activate it. The disease is induced when self-reactive TCRs are triggered in the vicinity and cross the blood-brain barrier to enter the central nervous system (CNS). Upon entering CNS, the T cells are reactivated by locally available APCs to initiate an inflammatory cascade (9).

MECHANISM OF RESISTANCE TO REGULATION IN EFFECTOR T CELLS IN MULTIPLE SCLEROSIS

FoxP3+ regulate T cells (Tregs) play a fundamental role to regulate the mechanism of resistance to suppression in order to counter immune homeostasis. This mechanism plays a crucial role to drive MS towards its peak disease activity (10). The following figure demonstrates the key factors involved in assisting T cells to resist suppression in MS. The T cells achieve the ability to escape regulation via several mechanisms. One of the mechanism is represented in the figure. Activation of self-reactive T cells causes an increase in interleukin (IL)-6/STAT-3 signaling as well as the release of granzyme B which suppresses the ability of CD4 FoxP3+ regulatory T cells to suppress the activity of effector T cells thus, progressing the diseased state in MS (11).

Figure 2: Mechanism of resistance to regulation in effector T cells in Multiple Sclerosis (15)

The PAR1 Receptor and KV1.3 ion channel induces neurotoxicity via Granzyme B

As described above, activation of T cells releases Granzyme B (GrB). Wang et al., determined that T cells which enter a self-reactive state are capable of causing damage to the neurons via various independent pathways like releasing Granzyme B (GrB). GrB drives the through cleaving and associating with membrane bound receptors, one of them being Notch-1. Notch-1 receptor supports formation of the inflammatory/demyelinating lesions in Multiple Sclerosis leading towards neuronal damage. The activation of GrB induces neuronal damage when it binds and cleaves the PAR-1 receptor. This governs the triggering of the PAR-1 consequently coupled with Gi which induces a reduction in cytosolic cAMP levels which further triggers the Kv1.3 channels to be opened. Opening of these potassium channels casts an oxidative stress on mitochondria leading towards mitochondrial dysfunction and activating caspase-3 which

governs apoptosis. Moreover, activated potassium channels also drive the activation and increased expression of Notch-1 receptor which supports formation of the inflammatory/demyelinating lesions in Multiple Sclerosis leading towards neuronal damage.

Figure 3: Possible signaling mechanism depicted in GrB-induced neuronal damage (15)

DISCUSSION

It has been proposed that MS, being a CD4 T-cell mediated disease, makes the effector T cells resistant to regulatory mechanisms. The T cells become dominantly tolerant towards regulation which is primarily induced via the association of T cells with CD4 FoxP3⁺ regulatory T cells (Tregs). This activity to suppress regulation keeps T cells activity in the CNS unchecked and contributes towards progression of the disease (11). Furthermore, T cells are functionally regulated by voltage-gated Kv1.3 potassium channels as they maintain the specific membrane polarization for the intake of calcium. There is a dominant association between Kv1.3 and calcium channels which play a fundamental role to understand the alterations induced in the T lymphocytes for the progression of MS (12). Thus, these channels serve as potential biomarkers and drug targets to manage and understand the broad spectral disease. Protease-activated receptor-1 (PAR-1) is a serine protease based GPCR. It is present in neurons and glial cells. The activation of PAR-1 which initiates tau phosphorylation mediates neuronal damage in motor neurons (4). It has been proven via experimental studies that GrB derives the cleavage of PAR-1 in neurons, mediating the

activation of the receptor and then increasing the expression of Kv1.3 channels and subsequently activating Notch-1 receptor. This contributes towards the exacerbation of neuronal damage and progression of the disease (13). The reason behind progressive neuronal damage in severe cases of MS. They depicted that PAR-1 is overexpressed in the neuronal cells exposed to the inflamed environment (14). The PAR1 expression further imperils the neurons due to being damaged by Granzyme B which triggers an apoptotic response in the cells.

GrB is proteinase stored in cytotoxic T cells and is released by activated T cells. It has a well determine role in suppressing viral infections and tumors. However, there have been experimental proofs for GrB to cause tissue rejection, autoimmune disease and inflammation of neurons. Experimental results have proven that when GrB binds to Gi bound PAR1, it just doesn't inhibit the receptor but degrades it. The degradation of these receptors have mass level effect on cAMP levels which progresses the neuronal damage. Normally, camp plays an important role in synaptic plasticity and long term memory development so it is a novel concept for GrB an PAR-1 receptor to mediate its role in neuronal damage. Another novel finding of interest for therapeutic purposes is the role played by Kv1.3 potassium channels. Potassium has a role in balancing ionic levels within the cell and enhancing permeability of plasma membrane in neurons and many other cells too. Henceforth, potassium channels also have the ability for changing intracellularly mediated events by being activated in the plasma membrane, membrane and Golgi apparatus. Moreover, it has also been hypothesized that these channels can act as secondary messengers in governing neuronal functions through the regulation of Notch-1 activation (13).

FUTURE PROSPECTS

This study helps to trace out a biochemical dysfunction which can pave way towards novel drug designing to manage MS. Tracing out cell signaling pathways which serve as a warning signal for the development or progression of a neuronal condition is beneficial in drug designing.

CONCLUSION

The role of GrB in progressing the neurite damage in Multiple Sclerosis is a novel study which has helped to elucidate MS biomarkers for screening and determining the state of the disease. It is interesting to address how T cell mediated response can bring the subsequent changes in the receptors and secondary messengers involved which exposes the neuronal cells to highly inflamed environment and thus increase the formation of myelinated lesions. These findings are very important to trace functional biomarkers of the disease and thus, can be useful to determine novel methods of drug designing and other therapeutic treatments for MS patients.

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